

Supplemental Material for “Orbital-ordered ferromagnetic insulating state in tensile-strained SrCoO₃ thin films”

Sheng-Chieh Huang,¹ Kanchan Sarkar,^{2,3} Renata M. Wentzcovitch,^{3,4,5} and Han Hsu^{1,*}

¹*Department of Physics, National Central University, Taoyuan City 320317, Taiwan*

²*Universität Ulm, Institute für Theoretische Chemie, Ulm 89081, Germany*

³*Department of Applied Physics and Applied Mathematics, Columbia University, New York, New York 10027, USA*

⁴*Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Columbia University, New York, New York 10027, USA*

⁵*Lamont–Doherty Earth Observatory, Columbia University, Palisades, New York 10964, USA*

S1. PAW datasets

In this work, we use the EPAW-1.0 code to generate efficient and robust PAW datasets (see Refs. 41 and 42 cited in the main text). The hybrid code uses genetic algorithms (GAs) to optimize all plausible PAW parameters to achieve the closest possible equation of states derived from all-electron (Wien2k) calculations for some benchmarked materials. Self-learning rules based on past explorations and exploitations of the search space determine the algorithmic parameters (of GAs). Accuracies obtained with these PAW datasets are close to all-electron calculations. The optimized parameters, which are used in the ATOMPAW program [N. A. W. Holzwarth *et al.*, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **135**, 329 (2001)] to generate the PAW datasets, are tabulated in Tables SI–SIII.

Table SI. Parameters to generate the PAW dataset for strontium.

Keywords and variables	Description
Sr 38	Atomic symbol and number
GGA-PBE scalarrelativistic loggrid 1500	XC functional and radial grid specification
5 4 4 0 0 0	max. n for each angular momentum: 5s4p4d
5 0 1	occupation numbers (5s1)
4 2 1	occupation numbers (4s1)
0 0 0	ends occupation section
c	1s treated as frozen core
c	2s treated as frozen core
c	3s treated as frozen core
v	4s treated as valence

v	5s treated as valence
c	2p treated as frozen core
c	3p treated as frozen core
v	4p treated as valence
c	3d treated as frozen core
v	4d treated as valence
2	max. l for basis and projector functions
2.3707 1.7683 2.2493 1.0728	radial values (Bohr) (rc, rshape, rvloc, rcore)
n	no further l = 0 basis functions
y	additional basis function for l = 1
2.6726	Eref1 energy (in Ry) for additional l = 1 basis function
n	no further l = 1 basis functions
y	additional basis function for l = 2
1.7613	Eref2 energy (in Ry) for additional l = 2 basis function
n	no further l = 2 basis functions
custom polynom2 7 10. vanderbiltortho	generation scheme for pseudo partial waves and projectors
3 0.0 ultrasoft	local pseudopotential parameters (lloc=3, Eloc=0 Ry)
1.7435	rc1 matching radius for first s partial wave
1.7096	rc2 matching radius for first s partial wave
1.7761	rc3 matching radius for first p partial wave
2.2220	rc4 matching radius for first p partial wave
2.2904	rc5 matching radius for first d partial wave
2.1782	rc6 matching radius for first d partial wave
XMLOUT	create data-set in xml format
default	
ABINITOUT	create data-set for ABINIT code
default	
PWSCFOUT	create data-set for Quantum ESPRESSO
UPFDX 0.0125d0 UPFXMIN -7.d0 UPFZMESH 50.d0	UPF grid parameters
PWPAWOUT	
END	

Table SII. Parameters to generate the PAW dataset for cobalt.

Keywords and variables	Description
Co 27	Atomic symbol and number
GGA-PBE scalarrelativistic loggrid 2001	XC functional and radial grid specification
4 3 3 0 0 0	max. n for each angular momentum: 4s3p3d
4 0 1	occupation numbers (4s1)
3 2 8	occupation numbers (3d8)
0 0 0	ends occupation section
c	1s treated as frozen core
c	2s treated as frozen core
v	3s treated as valence
v	4s treated as valence
c	2p treated as frozen core
v	3p treated as valence
v	3d treated as valence
2	max. l for basis and projector functions
2.1283 1.6425 0.8416 2.1080	radial values (Bohr) (rc, rshape, rvloc, rcore)
n	no further l = 0 basis functions
y	additional basis function for l = 1
2.9370	Eref1 energy (in Ry) for additional l = 1 basis function
n	no further l = 1 basis functions
y	additional basis function for l = 2
1.7616	Eref2 energy (in Ry) for additional l = 2 basis function
n	no further l = 2 basis functions
VANDERBILT	generation scheme for pseudo partial waves and projectors
bessel	local pseudopotential
2.1264	rc1 matching radius for first s partial wave
2.1023	rc2 matching radius for first s partial wave
1.7662	rc3 matching radius for first p partial wave
1.8501	rc4 matching radius for first p partial wave
1.9165	rc5 matching radius for first d partial wave
1.9772	rc6 matching radius for first d partial wave
XMLOUT	create data-set in xml format
default	
ABINITOUT	create data-set for ABINIT code
default	

PWSCFOUT	create data-set for Quantum ESPRESSO
UPFDX 0.0125d0 UPFXMIN -7.d0 UPFZMESH 50.d0	UPF grid parameters
PWPAWOUT	
END	

Table SIII. Parameters to generate the PAW dataset for oxygen.

Keywords and variables	Description
O 8	Atomic symbol and number
GGA-PBE scalarrelativistic loggrid 2001	XC functional and radial grid specification
2 2 0 0 0 0	max. n for each angular momentum: 2s2p
2 1 4	occupation numbers (2p4)
0 0 0	ends occupation section
c	1s treated as frozen core
v	2s treated as valence
v	2p treated as valence
1	max. l for basis and projector functions
1.5667 1.1505 1.3693 0.9536	radial values (Bohr) (rc, rshape, rvloc, rcore)
y	additional basis function for l = 0
2.0485	Eref0 energy (in Ry) for additional l = 1 basis function
n	no further l = 0 basis functions
y	additional basis function for l = 1
2.1155	Eref1 energy (in Ry) for additional l = 1 basis function
n	no further l = 1 basis functions
VANDERBILT	generation scheme for pseudo partial waves and projectors
2 2.5 ultrasoft	local pseudopotential parameters (lloc=2, Eloc=2.5 Ry)
1.0493	rc1 matching radius for first s partial wave
1.5316	rc2 matching radius for first s partial wave
1.4043	rc3 matching radius for first p partial wave
1.4039	rc4 matching radius for first p partial wave
XMLOUT	create data-set in xml format
default	
ABINITOUT	create data-set for ABINIT code

default	
PWSCFOUT	create data-set for Quantum ESPRESSO
UPFDX 0.0125d0 UPFXMIN -7.d0 UPFZMESH 50.d0	UPF grid parameters
PWPAWOUT	
END	

S2. Other Supplemental Tables

Table SIV. Energy minima (E_{min}) of all the obtained spin/orbital states in the FM and AFM orderings (A , C , and G types), along with the pseudocubic lattice parameter (a_{pc}). The equilibrium energy of bulk SrCoO₃ is used as the reference energy (0 eV). Here, $\Delta E_{AFM-FM} \equiv E_{min}^{AFM} - E_{min}^{FM}$ for the same particular spin/orbital state.

Spin/orbital states	E_{min} (meV/f.u.)	a_{pc} (Å)	ΔE_{AFM-FM} (meV/f.u.)
IS-m	-316.1714	3.8398	
IS-m (A-AFM)	-174.0441	3.8404	142.1273
IS-m (C-AFM)	-94.2624	3.9345	221.9090
IS-m (G-AFM)	85.8447	3.8760	402.0161
IS-hm	-350.1535	3.8795	
HS	-240.2239	3.9191	
HS (A-AFM)	-261.2003	3.9197	-20.9764
HS (C-AFM)	-172.6757	3.9265	67.5482
HS (G-AFM)	-208.5839	3.9355	31.6400
IH-rs	-345.1498	3.9145	
IH-rs (A-AFM)	-295.5513	3.9030	49.5985
IH-rs (C-AFM)	-177.6750	3.9427	167.4748
IH-rs (G-AFM)	-129.9989	3.9237	215.1509
HS-rs	-317.2497	3.8659	
HS-rs (A-AFM)	-272.1410	3.8566	45.1087
HS-rs (C-AFM)	-288.7261	3.9176	28.5236
HS-rs (G-AFM)	-232.1597	3.9037	85.0900
HS-c	-328.0290	3.8909	
HS-c (A-AFM)	-275.3949	3.8584	52.6341

HS-c (C-AFM)	-280.1578	3.9113	47.8712
HS-c (G-AFM)	-230.1026	3.9038	97.9264
HS-o3	-309.6676	3.9434	
HS-o3 (A-AFM)	-268.6616	3.9155	41.0060
HS-o3 (C-AFM)	-234.9283	3.9336	74.7393
HS-o3 (G-AFM)	-231.8576	3.9230	77.8100

Table SV. Total magnetization (M) of the HS-o3 state in all structures at $a_{pc} = 3.963 \text{ \AA}$ ($\varepsilon = 3\%$).
Note: Non-integer M is an indication of metallicity.

Imposed tilt	Before optimization	After optimization	M ($\mu_B/\text{f.u.}$)
$a^-a^-c^+$	$P2_1/c$ (M)	$P2_1/c$ (M)	3.00 (insulator)
$a^-a^-c^0$	$P2_1/c$ (M)	$P2_1/c$ (M)	3.00 (insulator)
$a^-a^-c^-$	$P\bar{1}$ (Tri)	$P2_1/c$ (M)	3.00 (insulator)
$a^0a^0c^-$	$P4_2/m$ (T)	$P4_2/m$ (T)	3.04
$a^+a^+c^-$	$P4_2/n$ (T)	$P4_2/m$ (T)	3.04
$a^0a^0c^+$	$Pnmm$ (O)	$Pnmm$ (O)	3.04
$a^+a^+c^0$	$P4_2/n$ (T)	$P4_2/n$ (T)	3.06
$a^+a^+c^+$	$P2/c$ (M)	$P2/c$ (M)	3.03
$a^0a^0c^0$	$P4_2/mnm$ (T)	$P4_2/mnm$ (T)	3.15

Table SVI. Total magnetization (M) of the HS-rs state in all structures at $a_{pc} = 3.963 \text{ \AA}$ ($\varepsilon = 3\%$).
Note: Non-integer M is an indication of metallicity.

Imposed tilt	Before optimization	After optimization	M ($\mu_B/\text{f.u.}$)
$a^-a^-c^0$	$C2/c$ (M)	$C2/c$ (M)	3.10
$a^-a^-c^+$	$P2_1/c$ (M)	$C2/c$ (M)	3.10
$a^-a^-c^-$	$C2/c$ (M)	$C2/c$ (M)	3.10
$a^+a^+c^0$	$P4/nnc$ (T)	$P4/nnc$ (T)	3.13

$a^+a^+c^+$	$Pnnn$ (O)	$P4/nnc$ (T)	3.13
$a^+a^+c^-$	$Ccca$ (O)	$Ccca$ (O)	3.33
$a^0a^0c^-$	$Ibam$ (O)	$Ibam$ (O)	3.34
$a^0a^0c^0$	$I4/mcm$ (T)	$I4/mcm$ (T)	3.33
$a^0a^0c^+$	$P4_2/mbc$ (T)	$P4_2/mbc$ (T)	3.33

Table SVII. Total magnetization (M) of the HS-c state in all structures at $a_{pc} = 3.963 \text{ \AA}$ ($\varepsilon = 3\%$).
Note: Non-integer M is an indication of metallicity.

Imposed tilt	Before optimization	After optimization	M ($\mu_B/\text{f.u.}$)
$a^-a^-c^0$	$Pnma$ (O)	$Pnma$ (O)	3.12
$a^-a^-c^+$	$Pnma$ (O)	$Pnma$ (O)	3.11
$a^-a^-c^-$	$P2_1/c$ (M)	$Pnma$ (O)	3.12
$a^+a^+c^0$	$I4/m$ (T)	$I4/m$ (T)	3.16
$a^+a^+c^+$	$C2/m$ (T)	$I4/m$ (T)	3.15
$a^+a^+c^-$	$P4_2/n$ (T)	$P4_2/n$ (T)	3.16
$a^0a^0c^-$	$P4_2/mbc$ (T)	$P4_2/mbc$ (T)	3.33
$a^0a^0c^0$	$P4/mbm$ (T)	$P4/mbm$ (T)	3.33
$a^0a^0c^+$	$Pbam$ (O)	$Pbam$ (O)	3.33

S3. Supplemental Figures

Fig. S1. Projected DOS onto the 3d orbitals of the (a) HS- d_{xy} , (b) HS- d_{yz} , and (c) HS- d_{xz} Co in the HS-o3 ($P2_1/c$) state at $a_{pc} = 3.963 \text{ \AA}$ ($\epsilon = 3\%$). Note that the HS- d_{yz} and HS- d_{xz} Co have nearly the same DOS curves, except the d_{xz} and d_{yz} curves are swapped.

Fig. S2. Effects of octahedral tilting on the electronic structure of the HS-o3 state. (a)–(e) Untilted $a^0a^0c^0$ structure ($P4_2/mnm$); (f)–(j) one-tilt $a^0a^0c^+$ structure (Pnm). For both structures, the total and projected DOS and the band structures are plotted. While no gap is opened in both structures, a tendency of gap opening can be observed when octahedral tilting is allowed. With further octahedral tilting about all three axes ($a^-a^+c^+$, $P2_1/c$ structure), a gap is opened, as shown in Fig. 4 in the main text.

Fig. S3. (a) HRTEM image of SrCoO₃ thin film at 3% tensile strain published in SM of Ref. 32; (b) atomic structure of the HS-o3 ($P2_1/c$) state obtained in our calculation, where blue and green spheres denote Co and Sr atoms, respectively. In panel (b), the lattice vectors (arrows) are based on the 20-atom cell of the $P2_1/c$ structure.

Fig. S4. A detailed comparison between the “ground state” reported in Ref. 20 [panels (a)–(c)] and the fully relaxed HS-c ($P4/mbm$) state obtained in this work [panels (d)–(h)]. Indicated by the orange circle in panel (d), the energy of the HS-c ($P4/mbm$) state is higher than the IS-hm ($Imma$) state by >40 meV/f.u.. Evident from panels (b) and (e), the atomic structures obtained from both works are nearly the same. In Ref. 20, the projected DOS onto both types of Co were added together without considering the orbital ordering [panel (c)]. By doing the same, we also obtain a highly similar DOS [panel (f)]. In panel (g), spin density is plotted to showcase the orbital ordering. As indicated in the band structure [panel (h)], the HS-c ($P4/mbm$) state is metallic.